

Human Resource Management Roles

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Introduction

The roles of Human Resource and Management play a vital role in the success of the organization. Internal recruitment is more valuable than external recruitment because it is less expensive, the employee's skills are well known and companies that do internal recruitment have an important tool to boost morale in the organization. Performance management is an important part of an organization. The most important thing is that it strengthens the supervisor and employee relationship and promotes commitment. Employee compensation and benefit programs are paramount in the hiring of potential and new employees and in decision making of the existing employee's. Therefore, a firm must consider the business strategy, cost, legal requirements, value, ability to pay and what type of benefits to offer in order to attract, motivate and maintain the most talented employees. The paper aims to discuss the roles of human resource management in terms of recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, compensation and benefits, labor relations and Global HRM.

Recruiting and Selection

Recruitment is the development of suitable techniques for attracting more and more candidates; it is the collection of pool of candidates. The purpose of recruitment and selection is to select the best fit candidate for the required job description (Gusdorf, 2009). The strategies of recruitment should be intelligently implemented as it is plays an important role in the success of the organization. To meet demands for talent brought about by business growth, a desire of new ideas and innovation are needed so the need to replace employees who leave, organizations

periodically turn to the outside labor market. The channels that are used for the internal recruitment and selection are job posting, employee referrals and temporary worker pools (Gusdorf, 2009). The advantages of internal recruitment are that the employee is already aware of the rules and regulations of the organization; furthermore, the employees are well adjusted according to the norms and culture of the organization. The main disadvantage of the internal recruitment is the lack of opportunity to get new and prepared talented employees because the current employees have the advantage to be hired regardless if they are very incompetent.

The channels that are used for the external recruitment and selection are employment agencies, job advertisement and referrals. An advantage of external recruitment is the possibility to get talented employees with new and creative ideas (Royal Holloway, 2010). Companies face these kinds of situations if external recruitment is done without considering the existing personnel. Organization could face high turnover if talented employees are not recognized and external candidates get the opportunity for high ranking positions. Once the recruitment is done, the selection of the right candidate is done in such a manner that right candidate is chosen for the right job.

Training and Development

Training is done for the better performance of the organization (Ford & Goldstein, 2002). Training can be of different types such as on-the job training, off-the job training and vestibule. The objective should be set before the training is given. There are two advantages to developing objectives. First, the objectives provide criteria for evaluating the training program. Second, the objectives provide trainers with the specific topics and content to focus on (Kraiger & Aguinis, 2009). This ensures that training programs are focusing on important topics and goals that have

certain meaning to trainees. The basic techniques include coaching, internships, apprenticeships, job rotation, job instruction methods, mentoring, case study, continuing education, college and correspondence courses, lectures, role- playing, programmed instruction and vestibule training (Kraiger & Aguinis, 2009). These training methods can be used to achieve either one or a combination of learning objectives: cognitive, non-cognitive and psychomotor. Rapidly changing technology and intensely competition are placing pressure on organizations (Ford & Goldstein, 2002). However, training and development has become increasingly popular as an HR technique for improving employee and managerial performance in organizations.

Performance Management

Performance management is an organized process by which an organization involves its employees, in improving the organizations efficiency and success of the company's mission and goals (Pulakos, 2004). Human resource management set goals on a regular basis. Employees are monitored on the basis of their performance and they are given feedback. Furthermore, formal and informal rewards are given to those who accomplish the mission. All five elements work together and support each other in maximizing performance management. The performance of the employee is based on certain factors. The factors include: safety, quality, productivity, teamwork, desired behavior and attendance (HRSA, 2011). A scale is used for each of the factor and each individual is evaluated according to the scale. Productivity is an important part of the performance management system.

Compensation and Benefits

Human resource management policies must be congruent with the firm's overall strategic approach. Organizations establish a formal compensation strategy that dictates how they will pay individuals. These include: basis for pay, skill-based pay, pay-for-knowledge programs or differential pay within a specific job, seniority based pay, performance based pay or pay rates relative to market rates (market rate, above market rate, or below market rate) (Bredensteiner & Raymond, 2000). These strategies carry significant financial costs as well as employee morale, motivation and productivity costs. In order to develop an effective and competitive pay system four basic tools are needed; updated job descriptions, a job evaluation method, pay surveys and pay structure (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2014). Having an updated job description gives key tools in the design of pay systems to identify important characteristics of each job to determine its worth to identify, define and weigh compensable factors (Bredensteiner & Raymond, 2000). The job evaluation method allows organizations to rate the worth of all jobs using a pre-determined system. Pay surveys identify and survey pay rates in relevant labor markets to obtain the fair market value.

Labor Relations

Labor Relations is the area that organizations have to deal with between employees and management. Union leaders can use to minimize conflicts between employers and employees such as strikes (Warner, 2012). Unions are the organizations that are formed for the purpose of representing their members' such as employees to deal with their issues. Collective bargaining agreement is used to make sure both sides are treated fair in terms of wages, hours of work, work environment and health care according to the contracts. The challenges union and non-union

environments faces are uncertain. Labor relations staff plays an integral part in the day-to-day operation for both employee and management issues (Malloy, 2014). Small and large organizations may differ on the amount of labor relations specialists; however, it is essential that qualified personnel are available to advise management, liaison with unions and assist employees on various aspects of labor relations (Warner, 2012). Labor relation officers are responsible for performing duties pertaining to employee relations including involuntary termination, demotion, suspension and reduction in pay.

Global HRM

In the past few decades, more and more companies are entering global markets by building facilities in various countries and exporting their goods. Since the companies set up their operations overseas, it would decrease their operating cost and attract more new customers. On the other hand, according to Svendsen, (2011) the international business increases and change the demands on human resource management and companies and employees have to understand the different cultures and laws in foreign countries. Brewster, Sparrow, Vernon & Houldsworth, (2011), stated that there are four factors affecting HRM in the global markets and those factors are culture, education, economic systems and political-legal systems. Among these four factors, the culture would be the most significant consideration if the company is operating internationally. Culture often determines the other three international influences and the effectiveness of various HRM practices. For example, people with different cultural background would have different opinions about how decision should be handled and what motivates employees. In addition, according to Hofstede study of culture, there are five dimension of culture and they are Individualism/collectivism, power distance concerns, uncertainty avoidance,

and masculinity/feminist and long term/short term orientation. Since, the companies have to realize the challenge and significant of cultural differences in the global markets, it is necessary for the companies to recruit managers with knowledge of various cultures and carefully elect individuals who would easily adapt to new environment. In addition, education and skill levels also play an important role global HRM because many foreign countries offer high skills and low labor cost, more and more companies are outsourcing their business or changing operating locations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, external recruitment is more difficult because it takes a long time and is more expensive because testing the outside sources is involved in this. In the era of globalization, more and more organizations are entering global market by operating foreign facilities. In order to enter the global markets successfully, the companies need employees to understand culture and local laws and be able to adapt them to different countries. Performance Management can be an effective tool with improving performance and productivity. It helps employees in increasing self-esteem and motivation. Different types of training can be given to meet the needs of the employees and the employers, the focus should be on the personal and strategic objectives to be attained. An effective training program depends upon a systematic approach including, need assessment, program design and evaluation of results. While, it is important to design the most comprehensive compensation and benefit package for the employees at all levels and check that the design represents a competitive salary that represents the company's reputation and mission statement and internally and externally consistent. When the U.S. labor relations system works effectively, efficiency and equity are achieved through collective bargaining, whereas, labor

relations specialists are representatives for the organization and are responsible for streamlining the process.

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